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THE SIGNIFICANCE OF THE MASTERPIECES OF OUR NATIONAL ART IN HUMAN LIFE

Abstract. This article focuses on national music culture, the history of Uzbek music art, its gradual development, and its important role in human life.

Keywords: Uzbek national music art, song and dance, folklore performance, world classical music lyrics, performance skills, voice range, national culture.

The musical culture of the Uzbek people has a very long history. In the course of development, the forms of performance closely related to the form and style of folk composition, traditional professional music, folk classical music, as well as folklore - amateur musical heritage, complemented each other. This musical heritage of ours is manifested even today as an aspect of our spirituality and culture. In the next four to five years, attention to our national-spiritual values, traditions, and cherished traditions that have not been forgotten, and the process of their reform became a priority. Respect and attention to our traditions, national values, and spiritual wealth have increased at the state level. Since the first years of independence, a lot of work has been done to preserve and restore the spiritual wealth left by our ancestors, in particular, musical culture, and to keep pace with the times. In this regard, our great spiritual wealth, which our ancestors left us as a legacy, serves as the main factor. It is known from time immemorial that our traditional songs, chants, musical culture, status performances, which are considered the main link of our spirituality, have always been recognized as spiritual food in the daily life of our people.

The people sought salvation from music in difficult days, and songs and music accompanied them in happy days, weddings and ceremonies. Because even today, in a time when we are realizing our identity, it is natural to rely on our national musical culture, which is a part of our great spirituality, inherited from our ancestors, and to turn to our traditional songs. All of these are important in the upbringing of a mature generation, in the formation of the spiritual worldview of young people. The art of singing, music, dance, folklore performance is one of the ancient art types that appeared and developed in close connection with the life and creativity of the people of national music. In particular, the traditional songs of our people are an immortal heritage, and today, as in all times, they answer "labbay". But at the same time, not only looking at history, but creating songs in accordance with today's spirit, which is one of the main factors in the development

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of our national ideology, is an important task for all specialists and artists engaged in musical art. Our country started a completely new society, a new life and a new life. There have been changes in people's hearts, thinking and imagination. It is no exaggeration to say that new views, new reforms and a new musical culture have entered the new Uzbekistan. Based on this, it is necessary for all directions of spiritual fronts to determine their goals and tasks. Moreover, in this regard, it is important to evaluate the special place of musical culture in spiritual life, to direct its power of influence towards the ideology of independence, and to understand that it is its main criterion. According to this principle, shifts are observed in our cultural life today. We would not be wrong if we say that the thoughts of the creators are directed towards these principles. Musical culture is distinguished by its diversity. In particular, the rich musical heritage of the Uzbek people, whose deep roots go back to ancient times, has not left our daily life.

It includes high examples of folk art, melody structure, folklore performance, musical and musical works developed in content, complex performance series called maqam music, and performance of epics. In addition, the creativity of folk composers, who have made significant contributions to the national musical culture in all periods, also has an important place. By the end of the 19th century, a period of changes began in Uzbek musical culture. This, of course, is related to the occupation of Turkestan by Russia. In this regard, it is necessary to study with a double vision. Because in some cases we observe the negative impact of national music on our culture, on the other hand, it should be recognized that there was a period of its own development. Because in our country, the scientific study of our national music art, the introduction of sheet music, had a significant impact on the development in the field of folklore and ethnography. In this regard, V. A. Uspensky, N. N. Mironov, Ye.Ye. It is necessary to mention the works of musicologists and ethnographers like Romanovskaya. Ilyas Akbarov, Mutal Burkhanov, Yunus Rajabi, Talibjon Sodikov, Mukhtar Ashrafiy learned from them. In addition, the introduction of piano music, opera and ballet, symphonic performance, world classical music, which are masterpieces of world musical culture, made a significant contribution to the comprehensive development of our musical culture. As a result, more than 20 volumes of books containing Uzbek folk music, songs, statuses were published. Our traditional music and songs have always called people to faith, humanity, kindness. Even today, without losing its relevance, it remains one of the main factors in the formation of the musical consciousness of the children of New Uzbekistan, as a tool in the upbringing of a well-rounded generation.

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